

A NOTE ON THE VOLUMETRIC ESTIMATION OF IODINE IN IODIDE

BY ARCOT VISWANATHAN AND SANKARANARAYANA GIREESAN

Vogel ("A Text-book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 1948, pp. 441, 447, Longmans-Green and Co., New York) recommends two volumetric methods* of estimating iodide in the absence of other halides, involving the use of potassium iodate or ceric sulphate and large quantities of concentrated hydrochloric acid. In the method herein described, less expensive and more commonly available materials are employed to estimate the iodide. Other halides, even if present, do not interfere with the results.

Reagents used are: (i) Standard potassium dichromate (B.D.H., A.R.), 5 g./litre = 0.10.20N. (ii). Sodium thiosulphate, 0.0998N. (iii) Standard N/10-KI solution (B.D.H., A.R), previously dried over sulphuric acid in a desiccator for a week or longer. (iv) Dilute sulphuric acid (8N). (v) Glycerol (pure, water-white; Lever Bros.). (vi). Chloroform or carbon tetrachloride. (pure). All solutions were prepared in distilled water (5 c.c.), boiled free of air.

Procedure.—KI solution (25 c.c.) was pipetted out into a 500 c.c. bottle carrying a tight fitting stopper. The potassium dichromate was added from a burette in slight excess (the required volume being calculated from the assumed normality of the iodide solution), the excess being limited to 2 or 3 c.c. Then dilute sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) was added and the bottle was stoppered, shaken and set aside in the dark for about 5 minutes for the complete oxidation of the iodide to iodine. Now, a well-shaken mixture of 30 c.c. of the sulphuric acid and 5 c.c. of the glycerol was added, washing the sides of the bottle, which was then stoppered, shaken and set aside in the dark. In about 15 minutes' time, the excess dichromate was completely reduced by the glycerol. Chloroform or carbon tetrachloride (5 c.c.) was added and the free iodine was titrated against the thiosulphate with continual shaking of the stoppered bottle. The end-point was cautiously approached, adding the solution from the burette dropwise, vigorously shaking the stoppered bottle after each addition. The end-point was reached when the violet colour of organic layer was discharged. Representative titre values are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

	Wt. of KI in 1 litre.					
KI.	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ .	Thio.	Calc.	Taken.	Deviation	
A 25 c.c.	28 c.c.	26.4 c.c.	17.50 g.	17.60 g.	-0.6 %	
B 25	27	25.2	16.70	16.80	-0.6	
C 25.	20	18.8	12.45	12.52	-0.3	
D 25	28	25.9	17.16	17.20	-0.23	

Though the deviations from the correct values are less than 1%, the low values (of A, B and C) are due to traces of moisture, persisting in the salt. Sample D furnished the best value as it was desiccated for a longer duration than the other samples.

The choice of the reducing agent is limited by several considerations. The reduction of dichromate should be effected at room temperature (30°) lest any application of heat to hasten the reaction should volatilise the iodine. At the same time, the reagents added or their oxidation products should be such that they would not consume any iodine. Of the several compounds tried, glycerol, under the conditions of the experiment, was found to be the best and was smoothly oxidised to carbon dioxide (Welwart, *Seifens. Ztg.*, 1936, 63, 372). A large excess of the dichromate is avoided as it requires considerable time to be reduced by the glycerol. In repeating the titrations of an iodide solution, the minimum excess (say of 1 c.c.) of the dichromate required, may be determined by calculation from a previous titre value and the normalities of the solutions. It may be mentioned that the addition of even 2 g. of potassium bromide initially to the iodide solution does not interfere with the titre value.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LOYOLA COLLEGE,
MADRAS-31.

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